

Classroom Management

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Abstract: This paper will cover everything an instructor ever wanted to know about classroom management and will cover a selection of different subjects. Some areas will include building culture, setting guidelines and anticipations, providing outcomes, and controlling classroom trouble. We will begin by identifying the instructor's role in classroom management.

Keywords: management, instructor, procedures, consequences, disruptions, routines, behaviour.

I. INTRODUCTION

Instructors must realize that the performance of the students within the classroom is a direct result of the instructor's environment. For example, a story about two different instructors. One group of students learns and behaves well for one instructor, while the same group behaves badly for another instructor. The change is the instructor. Instructors have a responsibility to generate a suitable environment for their students. It is also their responsibility to create a safe environment without bullying or violence in the classroom. Instructors must first concentrate on the students' behaviour, get their students' attention, and then focus on learning. Each classroom is different, so each instructor should have his own practical classroom management targets.

II. PRACTICAL CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

A. The Educator Personality

An educator is seen as an authority figure. When instructors introduce themselves in an authoritative manner, it helps them achieve the respect and belief required to lead students. The best way to be seen as an authority is to show confidence. A successful instructor must be confident in himself and in his capacity to teach. He'll never be in power if he's too scared to challenge his students. The bravery to challenge someone is a symbol of power.

An instructor must be direct when talking; his words must come out fluently. He should use strong statements to address misbehaviour so that instructors don't get rattled. They stay calm and maintain their calm. They must show that they are always in control. They are sure to stand up straight when teaching in front of the classroom. It is a way to show confidence and power. When addressing the students, good instructors speak with a deep and steady voice. They never rush their words.

Impressions are often built on appearance. There is a saying: "THE FIRST IMPRESSION LASTS". In a classroom, an instructor's dress code can have an influence on the learner's opinions and can create either a negative or positive kind of educational atmosphere. Meer, S.H. (2016). Reactions and attitudes are developed according to how a person looks, and in a setting like a classroom, the type of reactions from the students towards their instructors are vital to their achievement. As for the relationship between the instructor and his appearance, it is of great importance to the students, whether they are young in elementary school or old in advanced stages. The well-dressed educator attracts students at all stages. His look sends a message to students that he is organized and in control of his learners. (Staff, E. 2021, March 22).

B. Class Management

Class management means all the ins and outs that help teachers prepare productive classes. It also means the effort that teachers can make to make their classes better, more productive, and more comfortable places for them and their students to be creative and active.

Classroom management requires a lot of work that an instructor must do in advance before setting up and starting his class. An instructor can make his classroom a dynamic one, which will give him some confidence and control over his class (Jalbani, Laraib, Nasir, 2015). The first thing an instructor does is to prepare a solid plan. It is important to have a good plan before students even arrive on day one. In the first few days, an instructor demonstrates his plan in detail and guides the students to apply the necessary skills and behaviors to be successful throughout the learning process. To apply his plan, he should organize and set up the desks to make the class an open area for him to move around to monitor his students easily, and the students can communicate, especially if the instructor is doing group work. The next step before teaching is to check the white or smart board that an instructor intends to use

The relationship between instructors and learners is of great importance. Paying great attention to students' emotions makes a big difference to them. (MacSuga-Gage et al., 2012). There are simple ways for teachers to incorporate social-emotional learning into their daily routine. First thing in the morning, an instructor can begin the class with a check-in. He makes it a mission to ask a personal question. It doesn't have to be a complicated procedure. Even if the instructor is teaching online, it could be as simple as providing a kind "hello" to each student as they arrive in the morning by asking a question like "How do you feel today..." A teacher can address each student to show interest.

C. Routines and Procedures

Having clear, reliable routines and procedures makes students feel comfortable and secure when they know exactly what is expected of them on a daily basis. It is the responsibility of the instructors to provide a predictable and productive environment. Students will find it easier to meet their instructors' expectations if they establish daily routines. When students are talkative or noisy, an instructor should have some reliable signals that will keep them on task.

There are several areas where instructors can develop procedures for students to follow. There are procedures that will make students work like a fast machine. Well prepared procedures can create a structured, secure, and teacher-controlled class. There are many areas where teachers can develop the procedures required by students. It is great for the instructors to have a strategy for dispersing materials and a procedure for attendance so that everyone arrives on time. A procedure must be prepared for tests so that students remain calm and prevent speech, pay attention, and concentrate on their exam papers rather than looking left and right. In addition, the students must have procedures for group activities to stop talking to each other and organize speaking during teamwork. It is important to pay attention to the procedures for using the bathroom as they are useful at all levels, and the learning time is not interrupted when the student leaves class. Having a basket for students to put their homework in is a good idea, so teachers don't have to wait for students to hand it over.

An instructor needs a procedure for what students should do if they finish early. Their boredom will lead to misbehaviour. One solution is to use the "say hello" strategy. It's a quick and easy way to reinvigorate your students, improve their attentiveness, and reduce their boredom. Here's how it works:

When the instructors notice the students', attention weakening and boredom leaking in, they just let them get up, turn around the class, and say *hi* to their classmates.

Interacting with friends has a unique way of energizing and refreshing students. It feeds and refreshes their brains, gets the blood flowing, and releases the pent-up urge to engage in minor, though disruptive, unwanted behaviors. Surprising students will make this strategy work best. The instructor's role here is just to exclaim, "Stand up and say hello to your friends!" And then leave them alone and let them walk around for a couple of minutes.

This strategy can also be used shortly before a lesson that requires long attention, but instructors must be careful not to overdo it or it will lose some of its effectiveness.

One of the most effective and positive classroom management techniques is to have personal relationships with the students. Students are more connected and compatible when they love and admire their instructor, and the classroom environment is more enjoyable for the whole class when both the instructors and the students feel that they can rely on each other.

Clever instructors create lessons that take into consideration different learning patterns of learners. Some students understand the lesson best with lectures; others with images and visual aids; others with hands-on assignments; and others in teams or in individual learning time. Designing lessons that contain different patterns of learning methods gives students the opportunity to interact with the material in the best way for them.

Students are sensitive. They know when their instructors are excited about the subject. This will reflect their performance; they will be as enthusiastic as their instructors are. Students naturally feel the emotions of the teacher, whether they are anxious, bored, or excited, and they are likely to follow these signals and be more involved when they feel enthusiasm or interest.

The technique of getting the students' attention is suitable for any classroom. The idea is that students are expected to follow an easy mission when presented. Giving one easy task at the beginning of a class attracts the students' attention to the instructor. For example, the instructor says, "everyone's eyes on me," or "please look at the board."

Teaching starts long before the instructor's step into the classroom. Planning crucial and effective lessons and examining them for development will help class time flow more easily, preventing interruptions and delays and improving the excitement in the classroom. (Brophy, 2006).

Part of performing a successful lesson is mastering smooth shifting between subjects or activities. This helps prevent interruptions and unnecessary conversations and makes students feel encouraged to participate.

Like with everything else, students need to know what their instructors' expectations are from the first minute of the lecture. Grabbing the attention of the class by demonstrating the plan of the lecture and announcing what the next topic or activity will be and giving clear directions for any segment.

Group work allows students to work on building relationships, cooperating, and refining leading skills. In addition, it is a great way to get students more involved and engaged with the materials in the class and usually results in more learning and a student-to-student teaching method.

Playfulness is essential not only for children but for adults as well. Students deal with a variety of pressures and stress in their studies. Stress affects concentration in a negative way. It decreases the ability to learn. By encouraging non-stress classes, teachers help students learn better. To reduce stress, the instructor can include a joke, perform a game in class, promote creative presentations or projects, and generally keep an upbeat attitude in the classroom to make it more vital.

Students nowadays are addicted to mobile phones. Nowadays, in colleges and universities, it's difficult to do away with all the confusing technology that is being used in the classroom and being applied to the educational agenda. Even though some students may use laptops for notetaking, cell phones can still be restricted for more positive class time. This can be in the form of a phone box, so each student places his mobile once he enters the classroom, or instead, having students turn off their phones and keep them on a desk so that teachers can see that they are not being distracted.

D. classroom culture

It's necessary to create a classroom culture that will be the basis for support for classroom management and instruction. Building a classroom culture starts with a vision and aims for success. What instructors want to do is establish a shared vision with their students and ask them what they want out of the class and out of their lives. All students have essential human desires that drive their behavior. The instructor should monitor and guarantee that their students' demands are being met. The two primary theories in education are by Glasser and Maslow. Glasser says that teams will behave in a way to meet their demands. The first need is survival, as with all humans. They will need food, shelter, and love. The next need is to be energized. Students want to feel control over their lives. They want to feel independent. They want to be able to make choices that change their lives. Students, as all human beings are social creatures, everybody wants to belong, and so do students.

Students need some entertainment. On to Maslow's hierarchy, which is similar to Glasser's hierarchy; the most essential desires are at the bottom, and they move upward. These desires contain physiological safety, love and belonging, esteem, and, at the top, self-actualization.

The last step to creating a classroom culture is creating the proper environment for students' learning. Instructors must make their classrooms safe, tidy, and beautiful. The classroom should be neat and clean. It's not just the generous

responsibility; the instructors make sure students are not on top of one another. They need their own space. Lighting should be enough in the room. Students must be able to see the board clearly, to see their papers, and to organize the classroom in a way that limits traffic and lets students move easily. Instructors, as well, try their best to provide a calm space. Signs and posters in the classroom should be decorated nicely. Instructors put in mind their students' cultures. The classroom environment should be a mixture of the personality of the instructor and the personality of the students. That's how classrooms are decorated perfectly. (Gay, 2000).

The vision is to create some real-intelligent aims to meet the students' desires. Those aims must be specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely. Intelligent instructors come up with these class goals and focus on displaying these goals in the classroom on the walls. Using a growth mindset and nonstop work to achieve those goals and working harder and harder until they are achieved. Instructors make sure to emphasize the vision whenever they get a chance and give students a pat on the back to encourage them when they reach their goals.

Everything starts and ends with evaluation. Good instructors assess their development in the direction of the vision. Some simple vision examples for students, like an increase in attendance or an increase in reading skills or building a family-like atmosphere in the classroom, encouraging relationships with their classmates, reducing bullying, will help students move on the right track in their lives.

The instructor's role in creating a classroom culture is to combine practices and ideas. Instructors can use classroom practices and festivals to bring the class together. A successful instructor knows his students' birthdays and celebrates them. He can also plan a field trip for his class. For example, he can get them out of the college, or bring a pet to the class, something like a cat, a bird, or a fish. It's lovely when some high school teachers greet their students with a special greeting. Occasionally, they can show a movie to break their routine as a reward. Another good idea is that when they send a positive note to students' homes, those notes will make all the difference in the world for those adults. Setting a monthly competition like "The Student of the Month" and changing it up every month. Instructors display all their students' work, showing the whole school that their instructors are proud of them.

E. classroom systems and regulations.

It is very important to establish rules for classrooms because those rules will regulate both time and students' behaviors. It is important to give students a clear idea of the behavior expected of them. When creating rules, instructors must set 4 to 6 rules (not exceed 6 rules). Relying on students to memorize these rules is a big mistake. These rules must be written and hung somewhere in the classroom for all students to see easily. Make it clearly written in a positive way, for example, [*You must arrive on time*]. instead of "*don't be late.*" The instructor should also avoid writing long sentences. A smart instructor gives the students an opportunity to express their opinions on these rules, whether they have a problem with any of them, or if they have any suggestions about the rules. After that, the instructor has the right to impose and apply the rules to all students all the time, without exceptions. Justice is the key for the instructor to enforce the rules day by day. This means that all students are forced to respect and follow the laws in a fair manner. The instructor himself must follow them. Controlling a class begins by spreading justice and attention among students, and then by talented teachers who skilfully use body language and voice tone. An instructor cannot impose rules on some students while overlooking others. Some laws may need to be delayed in some cases until he finishes his explanation and then he implements the penalty shortly thereafter. Instructors should avoid leaving the manager to set those rules for him. It is often a sign of weakness.

F. Consequences

Controlling the student's behavior within the classroom is one of the most important problems that face teachers in the performance of their mission and even one of the most difficult tasks. The professor needs to remove all obstacles to his teaching duties in the classrooms. (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006).

The consequences should be known to the students. They should know what they're getting into when they misbehave. They should stress the cause-and-effect relationship and clearly explain to the student what caused the consequences when they misbehave. Students must understand that it's not personal when you issue them consequences. On the other hand, instructors reinforce positive behaviors by giving rewards like high grades to those who behave themselves.

There are a few examples of the consequences a teacher can apply to those who misbehave, like sending email to parents, demonstrating the behavior committed by the student, and imposing punishment sentenced by the teacher. Another punishment is detention, which is holding students after school to change their behavior and resolve problems. A third

way is moving students' seats because they disturb those around them. A fourth example of punishment is asking misbehaving students to take a time out. The goal of the time limit is not to be a penalty but to give students a few minutes to calm down, regain control, and think about what should happen next. Finally, a teacher makes students write apologies.

G. Consequences Documentation

A teacher once said, "If it wasn't documented, then it didn't happen." Teachers should record any serious incidents that they have with their students. It's for the teachers' own security. When teachers write down what happened, students know it's on their record. It makes a difference when teachers write down what happened word for word, so everybody knows what was said. Writing down accurate dates, times, places, witnesses, and being as specific as possible is an indication that the teacher is very organized. Keeping a parent log to store all documents in the same place, e.g., in a file cabinet. However, today it's best to be digitally organized, because a soft copy will work much better than a hard copy.

H. Consequences of Implementation

A. The question is when should teachers reply to behaviors and apply consequences? If at any time somebody's safety is in danger, the instructor must intervene. Instructors should never allow students to interrupt the learning process. Immediately, they must deal with the disrupter, and if any of those four to six rules, created by the professor, are broken, he must respond as quickly as possible, unless it's a minor interruption. The consequences should be logical and appropriate to the behavior. The behavior and punishment should have a compatible relationship. If a student throws some papers on the floor, the teacher asks him politely to pick them up. One important thing is that the teacher maintains the student's self-esteem and respect even if he has behaved badly.

There are three kinds of disruptions: minor, major, and chronic ones. Minor troubles are behaviors that do not deserve punishment but are still annoying, including students tapping their pencils, murmuring, doodling, giggling, etc. One method to deal with this is to quietly and quickly get near the annoying student to grab his attention during the middle of the lecture. To avoid interrupting the lesson, teachers may give the student a quick glance or use a different method to indicate students who are not paying attention or are annoying by leaving a small note on their desk. A teacher may quickly say the students' names to get them back on track. A gentle way to deal with minor interruptions is to quietly tap on the student's desk, but the most important thing is to realize that teachers don't want to be the ones to stop the flow of the lecture. A minor problem should not ruin the learning process. Unlike major disruptions Teachers don't have to exaggerate and sometimes they could just ignore the minor bad behaviors but be careful with the ignoring technique.

long-lasting troubles that continue even after being addressed by the teacher. The best way to deal with this kind of disruption is to gradually increase the degree of consequences. On the other hand, teachers must be sure to document the number of times the bad behavior is repeated by the students. The teacher tells the student that the consequence is a result of his bad behavior. Both teachers and students should move forward towards conflict resolution strategies. One suggestion for chronic misbehavior is to have the student sign a behavior deal. Parents can be involved not only with the deal but also with a scheduled conference or a phone call to find the cause of this chronic behavioral problem committed by their sons or daughters. Students with chronic behavior must conduct a functional behavioral evaluation.

Students are different, so teachers are going to find the most effective consequence for each individual student. For the teacher, it always helps to take some notes and reflect on what has been working and what hasn't been working.

The third type of disruption is major disruptions. These types of disruptions put both teachers and students at risk. Some major disruptions include destruction of school property; fighting; starting fires; making threats; and bringing in weapons. Dealing with these types of behaviors is very fatal, so teachers must be very cautious.

As a start to the semester, a teacher can take his students on an introductory tour to the most important places in the school building, such as the college clinic and the nearest first aid box. Teachers as well as students must read their academy policy at the beginning of a semester. Teachers are going to routinely reteach rules and procedures. Students are going to forget, especially after a vacation. It's important to try and understand some of the common reasons why students misbehave. Those reasons include unclear limits, wanting attention, boredom, avoiding work-related issues, Teachers should carefully read the students' files and check all medical issues. Unlike with minor disruptions, teachers must contact their administrator with major incidents. If teachers feel threatened, they must speak with their teacher's union about what steps to take to protect themselves. (Hernandez & Fister, 2001).

I. Instruction for classroom management

Well planned and engaging lessons will decrease student behavior problems. To avoid boredom, clever teachers change up their lessons. It is a great mistake to do the same routine every day. Clear objectives will keep students on task, working towards a goal. (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015; Everston & Weinstein, 2006). Inquiry-based learning activities are engaging in fostering problem-solving skills. Hard-working teachers use fun, hands-on learning activities like bridge building. Many teachers have seen wonders in their classrooms because they talk to their students and find their interest in using that knowledge to create activities and develop course programs. Successful teachers pay great attention when they plan the lessons. Their main goal is to let different instruction and ideas run smoothly. When instructions are clearly demonstrated, students will enjoy the class time. Students require work that is challenging but can be applied. Teachers must pick their battles; they do not have to fight a war daily. It's okay when students misbehave; many of their problems aren't about the teacher. Classroom management is something a teacher must work on, making it his number one priority.

III. CONCLUSION

These classroom management strategies will help both teachers and students make the most of the classroom environment. With some helpful tools, the class will be more collaborative, exciting, and material-interested. Whether these classroom management techniques are applied to manage a class of annoying teenagers, or an academy lecture hall, instructors and students will benefit from a more focused and innovative classroom environment.

Many people, inside and outside of education, try their best to climb the ladder of success till they reach a certain point where they realize that their ladder was leaning up against the wrong wall. They discover that much of their time and energy has been wasted because their objectives were not compatible with their beliefs and principles. They were disabled by what was believed to be a victory, but it cost them things that truly mattered.

Teachers who want to mark the lives of their students in positive ways must admit that they are weak but, at the same time, are eager to grow and increase their abilities. The core of their vision is their vital desire to do their best for the student, and they believe that by doing a great job with small things, great things will happen.

This paper shows the basic format of research paper preparation and can be used as template writing research paper. Conclusion of research paper is between 150 to 350 words.

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